

Funerary Cenotes of the Mayas

also known as “Cenotes as mortuary chambers among the pre-Hispanic Maya”

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Entry tags: Mesoamerican Religions, Religious Group, Cemetery, Mayan, Mesoamerica, Yucatan Peninsula, Language, Mayan Religions, Religious Place, Cave or Cavern

Since ancient times, the caves and cenotes of the Yucatan Peninsula have been settings of great importance for the Maya. During pre-Hispanic times they were depositories of human remains and various types of offerings. Traditionally, the presence of human skeletons in cenotes was explained as the result of human sacrifices; however, in some of them no evidence has been found associating them with this practice. Although it is not doubted that many of the skeletons recovered from the Sacred Cenote of Chichén Itzá correspond to sacrificed characters, there are cases in which it is suggested that the individuals were deposited as part of their rituals and funerary treatments. Such is the case of Cenote Las Calaveras, in which 122 skeletons have been counted to date, of which the remains of 23 individuals were analyzed.

Date Range: 0 CE - 300 CE

Region: Quintana Roo

Region tags: Maya, Mexico, Mesoamerica, Mesoamerica, Northern Maya

Cenotes are sinkholes that have collapsed as a result of karstification. Its name comes from the Mayan *ts'onot* which means well or cavern with water. The cenote Las Calaveras is part of the archaeological site of Punta Laguna, inside the Natural Protected Area called *Otoch Maax Yetel Co* which means "House of the Monkey and the Puma". For further reference, it is located 18 km northeast of the Archaeological Zone of Cobá. The archaeological site of Punta Laguna consists of an area approximately 1 km long in an E-W direction and 600 m N-S. It has at least 36 structures and four large polygonal platforms, three stelae, several altars, a cove, where there are four caves, a cenote and a cave further west of the cove. The part that seems to be the oldest dates back to the Classic and is located 300 m. east of the cove; the settlement grew around it, so Postclassic buildings were erected to the north and northeast of the center. It is part of the so-called Eastern Coast, due to its characteristic architecture. Its origins seem to begin in the Late Preclassic period and then gain momentum during the Postclassic.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Rojas Sandoval Carmen, 2011, Los cenotes como cámaras mortuorias entre los mayas prehispánicos. Tesis de Maestría en Arqueología. Escuela Nacional de Antropología e Historia. México. Director de tesis Dr. Manuel Gándara Vázquez.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: https://www.academia.edu/117893081/Cenotes_como_camaras_funerarias_Carmen_Rojas
- Source 1 URL: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AhUGCZCwS5o&list=PLPpHDnfiPtjMmpTliiODGWHSkrf_G6Da
- Source 1 Description: México biocultural - Área de protección de flora y fauna Otoch Ma´ax Yetel Kool

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

- Scientific

Years of excavation:

- Year range: 2002-2012

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 90 BCE - 400 CE

Status of Participants: Elite Religious Specialists

Name of excavation

- Official or descriptive name: Proyecto Atlas Arqueológico de Cenotes y Proyecto Cementerios Acuáticos Mayas

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

- Tree, grove, or forest
- Water source
- Body of water (as distinct from source)
- Cave
- Other [specify]: Lagoons

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

- I don't know

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

- No

Notes: There is a small maya village of the Punta Laguna community.

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

- Yes

Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

- Yes

Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

- Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

- No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

- Yes

A single structure

- No

One single feature

– Mound

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Social

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Field doesn't know

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:
– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:
– Yes

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

↳ Specify
– Religious specialists affiliated with political entity

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– No

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– I don't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Funerary purposes.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

Notes: Lagoons

Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

Notes: Cenote and caves

Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and

Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:
– I don't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:
Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.
– Square meters: 250

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
– Height, meters: 15

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
– Square meters: 250

↳ Height of average monument, meters:
– Height, meters: 15

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth
– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Wood

– No

↳ Grass

– No

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: .

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– No

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– No

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Sí

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Sí

↳ For the worship of a deceased person(s):
– Sí

↳ For the worship of a deified human:
– No lo sé

↳ For the worship of a deceased hero:
– No lo sé

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Yes

↳ Cremation:
– No

↳ Mummification:
– No

↳ Interment:
– Yes
Notes: Funerary treatment in an aquatic environment

↳ Cannibalism:
– No

↳ Exposure to the elements:
– Yes

Notes: Water

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

↳ Secondary burial:

– Yes

Notes: Maybe at some cases

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No lo sé

Notes: maybe at some cases

↳ Other intensive (time/resources expended) treatment [Specify]:

– Other [specify]: Ritual immersion of the dead.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No lo sé

Notes: Probably

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– No

↳ Valuable/precious items:

– Yes

Notes: Suntuary ceramic

↳ Significant value:

Gold, jade, intensely worked objects, or meaningful symbolic value

– No

↳ Some value, valuable or useful objects:

– Yes

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: wood ring and deer antler

↳ Other

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

↳ Family tomb/crypt:

– I don't know

↳ Domestic context:

Interred beneath floors of house, or in areas of domestic activity

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: no

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No lo sé

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No lo sé

Are previously human spirits present:

– No lo sé

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No lo sé

Notes: Probablemente

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No lo sé

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No lo sé

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No lo sé

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No lo sé

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No lo sé

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No lo sé

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– No lo sé

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– No lo sé

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No lo sé

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No lo sé

Are material offerings present:

– No lo sé

Notes: Ceramica suntuaria

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– No lo sé

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– No lo sé

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– No lo sé

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No lo sé

Are festivals present:

– No lo sé

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No lo sé

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No lo sé

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– No lo sé

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No lo sé

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– No lo sé

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– No lo sé

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– No lo sé

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– No lo sé

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No